

SECURED DATA TRANSMISSION FOR WIRELESS NETWORK

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ABSTRACT

Now a days while data transmission, security is one of the major issues for data transmission over wireless networks. Existing system utilizes security algorithm for providing secure data transmission over networks but in our proposed system, security for data transmission can be achieved without any use of security algorithm. Our proposed system will be utilizing 'mobility cluster head' instead of security algorithms for data transmission over wireless networks. 'Mobility Cluster Head' will contain the information of each node within a wireless network and if any unauthorized node will try to hack the information then 'Mobility Cluster Head' or Global Inspector(GI) secure the configured network from the unidentified attackers. Proposed System will secure data transmission to dynamically route packets between each source and destination. For data transmission, two different protocols i.e. Ad-hoc On Demand Distance Vector (AODV) and Destination Sequence Distance Vector (DSDV) will be utilized which will maintain the routing table of the network. Also, we will try to detect which protocol will be more efficient for data transmission without use of any security algorithm over wireless network.

Keywords: Data transmission, Dynamic routing, AODV, DSDV, Mobility Cluster Head, Global Inspector (GI)

1. Introduction

In the past year, various security-enhanced measures i.e. various algorithms have been proposed to improve the security of data transmission over the network [1].

Now days the use of internet is increase day by day as well as the hacking of data also rapidly increases. The main purpose of proposed system is to provide security for wireless network using 'Global Inspector' or 'Mobility Cluster Head'.

In this paper we will use two protocols i.e. Destination Sequence Distance Vector Routing Protocol (DSDV) [3] and Ad Hoc On-Demand Vector routing protocol (AODV) will be utilized for maintain the routing table of the network. Finally we will conclude which protocol is better for data transmission. We will propose a system using front end that is Network Simulator (NS2).

2. Existing System

In the past year, various security-enhanced measures have been proposed to improve the security of data transmission over the networks includes the cryptographic algorithm and security routing methods for detecting the various threats, worms, virus over the internet[6].

There are some drawbacks in previous system:

- There is overhead if any fault of routing path, they need to setup a new path.
- They require complete knowledge of network for implementation.

3. Objective

The system will be utilizing 'mobility cluster head' instead of security algorithms for data transmission over wireless networks. 'Mobility Cluster Head' will contain the information of each node within a wireless network and if any unauthorized node will try to hack the information then 'Mobility Cluster Head' or Global Inspector(GI) secure the configured network from the unidentified attackers.

For data transmission we will use two protocols AODV (Ad hoc On Demand Distance Vector) and DSDV (Destination Sequenced Distance Vector). AODV is capable of unicast and multicast. AODV is reactive protocol [2] and DSDV is proactive protocol [3].

4. Proposed plan of Work

In proposed system we will provide the security while communicating through a network and for communication purpose we will use two protocols DSDV and AODV. Data packet is transfer through random paths this process is nothing but the "Randomization Process".

A. AODV--Ad Hoc On-Demand Vector routing protocol (AODV) is on-demand routing protocol. AODV maintains and uses an efficient method of routing that reduces network load by broadcasting route discovery mechanism and by dynamically updating routing information at each intermediate node. AODV protocol is Reactive in nature means route is generated only on demand to reduce the routing load. AODV is capable of both unicast and multicast routing [10].

B. DSDV-- Destination Sequenced Distance Vector [10] is a loop free routing protocol in which the shortest-path calculation is based on the Bellman-Ford algorithm. Data packets are transmitted between the nodes using routing tables stored at each node. Each routing table contains all the possible destinations from a node to any other node in the network and also the number of hops to each destination. The protocol has two main attributes: to avoid loops, to reduce high routing overhead.

C. Randomization process—In order to reduce the access of data by unidentified user over a specific link we will used 'Randomization process'. Randomization is process for making something random that means it select random sequence of path and avoids the transmission of packet from same path. Randomization process is used for transferring the data from source to destination, using this process unauthorized user can't access the data.

Proposed system deals with providing security for wireless network at the time of data transmission. For the proof of the concept we are building masquerade attack which takes fake identity within the network. The Sybil[5] or masquerade attack[4]. Sybil or masquerade attack is attack which takes information of any node in the network and act as that node which is real node place within the network.

System will be utilizing 'mobility cluster head' instead of security algorithms. 'Mobility Cluster Head' will contain the information of each node within a wireless network like IP Address, Node Location etc. and if any unauthorized node will try to hack the information then 'Mobility Cluster Head' or Global Inspector(GI) check there IP address and if IP address is not present in mobility cluster head then it does not allow to perform any task means any transferring of data and it consider as that node is unauthorized node and they secure the configured network from the unidentified attackers[4].

This is done using Network Simulator (NS2). Network simulator is software that simulates the performance of the network without the real network. There are two output of NS2 a nam file and tr file. A nam file is used for graphical representation also provides visualize interpretation of the network topology created. The other file i.e.tr file can be also say as the trace data analyzer shows the information of Xgraph and Trace graph. Xgraph shows the interactive plotting and graphing. In which graph shows all types of the information delay, data receive, send and drop separately. Trace file show the information of sending packets and what time the packet

will be send that means it gives static result of program [8,9].The file contain the information in the sequence as like it contain information firstly of the event type i.e send or receive, Event time, current node, current processing layer, packet type, packet size, source ID, destination ID i.e. time to leave, next hop address, TCP sequence no., Acknowledge number.

Comparative study of AODV and DSDV routing protocol—AODV (Ad hoc on-demand vector protocol) and DSDV (Destination Sequenced Distance Vector) both protocol is concern with same family of protocol i.e. Dynamic routing protocol, but AODV is reactive in nature and DSDV is proactive in nature. We will compare this two dynamic routing protocol and find which protocol is used for better transmission of data for wireless network.

5. Conclusion

After studying this we will conclude that using this system data will be transmitted in secured manner without any use of security algorithm. We will use “Mobility Cluster Head or Global Inspector” instead of any security algorithm, unauthorized node can’t access the data And also comparative study of AODV and DSDV conclude that which protocol is better for data transmission in wireless network.

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